

A cautionary reflection on (pseudo-)synthetic data from deep learning on personal data

Fabio Ricciato^[0000–0002–4785–3858]

Eurostat, Rue Alphonse Weicker 5, Luxembourg
fabio.ricciato@ec.eurostat.eu

Abstract. In this paper we consider “synthetic data” derived from personal data through deep learning. We argue that the “synthetic data” produced by high-dimensional generative networks should be distinguished from other species of “synthetic data” produced by traditional human-designed low-dimensional mechanisms. Taking inspiration from Channel Coding theory, we introduce the notion of “privacy-deceptive coding” to signify any mechanism that conceal the training data, fully or partially, into the newly “generated” data that appear different at face value from the original data. We show one prominent example of privacy-deceptive coding based on multivariate interpolation, whereby a group of n source points gets “encoded” into a different set of $\tilde{n} \geq n$ points laying on the same interpolating curve with n degrees of freedom. We warn on the possibility that a large-scale generative network trained on real data may end up learning some sort of privacy-deceptive mechanism, similar to the one presented here. The plausibility and the implications of this possibility from the perspective of data protection are discussed. One important consequence is that the “burden of proof” that the generative network has not actually learned any privacy-deceptive coding lies with their proponents. This proof may be difficult to achieve for large-scale networks with billions of parameters. Lacking this proof, we argue that the new “generated” data set should be considered as a sophisticated form of pseudonymisation, not anonymisation, and the resulting data should be referred to as “pseudo-synthetic” rather than “synthetic” data.

Keywords: Synthetic Data · Deep Learning · Pseudonymisation · GDPR

1 Introduction

The outstanding success of Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in numerous business fields is changing the perception by the society of the *value* as well as of the *risks* associated with personal data. Like oil unleashes its internal latent energy (but also several pollutants) when it fuels the combustion engine, data gets more valuable (but also more dangerous) when they fuel the modern powerful AI/ML “engines”. The availability of more capable and powerful AI/ML technology increases the appetite for granular data and the pressures on those who hold the data to make them available to those that own the AI/ML engines. But sharing and release of granular data come with high risks and is

subject to legal compliance with data protection legislation. The combination of increasing value but also increasing perception of the risks associated to data sharing concur to amplify the interest by researchers (and the investment by the business) for solution approaches that, like “green” pollution-free combustion, promise to spur “safe sharing” of granular data.

One of the solutions approach most actively investigated by different research communities (and proposed by well-funded startups) relies on the generation of “synthetic data” based on large-scale AI/ML models trained on real data. In other words, while on one side AI/ML increases the appetite for granular data, on the other side it seems to provide an appealing recipe for enabling “safe sharing” of granular data in the form of “synthetic data”.

The idea of leveraging (semi-)synthetic data derived from confidential data is not at all new: over the last few decades the Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) community has developed different methods to trade-off “privacy” vs. “utility” (see e.g. [1,2]). However, outside the circle of researchers and specialists, there seems to be a misguided perception that, when “generated” by large-scale AI/ML models, synthetic data magically leap over the “privacy-vs-utility” trade-off frontier, and mystically deliver almost full utility at essentially zero privacy risk – aren’t these data “synthetic” therefore artificial at the end of the day?

With this paper, and line with recent work by other authors [3,4], we provide an additional contribution towards demystifying this increasingly popular narrative. Among the factors that contribute to the confusion is probably the overload of the term “synthetic data” to refer to fundamentally different paradigms. Therefore, we start by proposing a taxonomy and a differentiated terminology to distinguish the different “synthetic data” paradigms. We propose to adopt the term “pseudo-synthetic data” to refer to data produced by large-scale generative models trained on real data, for the reasons that are presented below.

Along the discussion, we introduce the notion of “privacy-deceptive coding” to refer to mechanisms that conceal, rather than remove, personal information from the source data into the new data. We present qualitatively a simple example of privacy-deceptive coding based on multivariate polynomial interpolation. Based on this, we elaborate on the possibility (and plausibility) that a large-scale over-parameterised AI/ML model may end up learning some similar scheme. From there we claim that pseudo-synthetic data based on deep learning should be considered in GDPR terms as an advanced form of “pseudonymisation”, rather than “anonymisation”, unless a conclusive proof is given that the model has not learned any structural mechanisms that is akin to constitute some form of privacy-deception coding.

Our intention here is not to provide a conclusive word, but rather to propose an alternative angle of view, and in this way contribute to the discussion between technology specialists and legal specialists.

2 Data generation paradigms: synthetic, semi-synthetic and pseudo-synthetic

In several scientific and technology fields it is customary to generate “synthetic data” serving the purpose of testing the performance of some system, real or simulated, in certain configurable conditions.

In the most genuinely “synthetic” scenario, depicted in Fig. 1(a), both *the logic $g()$ and the parameters \mathbf{z}* of the data generator are fully specified by a human expert with direct knowledge of the real-world phenomenon of interest (in engineering disciplines the generator is often called “simulator”). This scenario does not involve any real-world data.

In a slightly more sophisticated scenario, some real data \mathbf{x} are collected from the real-world phenomenon of interest, and the parameters of the synthetic data generator \mathbf{z} are fit to the real data \mathbf{x} through some fitting or regression function $r()$, i.e. $\mathbf{z} = r(\mathbf{x})$. This scenario is depicted in Fig. 1(b).

We claim that the **dimensionality of the parameter space \mathbf{z}** plays a critical role also for what concerns the legal aspects of personal data protection. We distinguish the “low-dimensionality” and “high-dimensionality” regimes. Let $|\mathbf{z}|$ denote the number of parameters in the generator function and $[\mathbf{x}]$ the intrinsic dimensionality of the input data. The low-dimensional regime, characterised by $|\mathbf{z}| \ll [\mathbf{x}]$, corresponds to human-designed system or to “classical” under-parameterised ML systems. The high-dimensional regime, for which $|\mathbf{z}| > [\mathbf{x}]$, refers to over-parameterised ML models and “deep” networks, for which data overfitting is the norm [5].

In ML theory these two regimes are clearly distinguished and treated separately (see e.g. [6,7]). They are known to display different characteristics and structural mechanisms. Accordingly, we claim that these regimes should be considered and treated separately *also from a legal standpoint*: what is claimed or proved for the low-dimensional regime may not necessarily hold true for the high-dimensional regime, and vice-versa, also from the perspective of personal data protection. The low-dimensional case $|\mathbf{z}| \ll [\mathbf{x}]$, depicted in Fig. 1(b), is the traditional approach, and the only one considered until the recent advent of large-scale AI/ML and deep learning. In the low-dimensional case of Fig. 1(b), the data generator $g()$ and the fitting function $r()$ are *parsimonious*, i.e., they involve a relatively small number of parameters, and also *interpretable*, in the sense that such parameters have known semantics (they typically encode descriptive summaries of aggregate quantities, moments of marginal distributions, hyper-parameters of analytic families, correlation coefficients, counts, and alike). In this scenario, *parsimony and interpretability* allow to assess explicitly the privacy risk, i.e., to assess whether and how much personal information about \mathbf{x} is conveyed through \mathbf{z} into the new data $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ ¹. In other words, the “dimensional-

¹ The risk of conveying personal information from \mathbf{x} into $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$, that is the focus of our contribution, should be distinguished from the risk that some genuinely artificial data points match incidentally real-world data points. The latter case is susceptible of producing at least a “reputational risk” for the data holder [8, Section 3.3.3.1].

ity bottleneck” $|z|$ facilitates the task of limiting or blocking the conduction of personal information from x through z to \tilde{x} .

In the scenario of Fig. 1(b) the data generation logic $x \rightarrow z \rightarrow \tilde{x}$ is mediated by the parameter set z . A third possible scenario is depicted in Fig. 1(c), where the data \tilde{x} are derived directly from x , formally $x \rightarrow \tilde{x}$, without the mediation of explicit globally descriptive parameters. The derivation function $s()$ is designed to act selectively on a subset of data elements (variables, records, or combinations thereof). The selected elements can be subject to value swapping, replacement, randomisation, generalisation etc. Since the resulting data set \tilde{x} contains a mixture of real and “synthetic” elements, we choose to denote it by the term “semi-synthetic” in order to distinguish it from the previous scenario. In this scenario, the derivation function $h()$ is designed by a human expert and therefore it is intrinsically *parsimonious* and *interpretable* – hence *auditable*. From the detailed knowledge of the derivation mechanism $h()$, it is possible in principle to assess the risk of backwards inference and keep it under control, at the cost of some *loss of fidelity*, hence of *utility* of the new data for certain analysis tasks. In other words, parsimony and interpretability of the derivation logic $s()$ allow to control explicitly the utility-privacy trade-off. In the last decades the SDC community has developed different proposals based on this scenario (see [1,2] and references therein).

More recently, following the outstanding success of large-scale AI/ML models and deep learning in other application fields, a new computationally-intensive high-dimensional paradigm has emerged alongside the traditional design-based low-dimensional one. In this new paradigm, depicted in Fig. 1(d), the generation of \tilde{x} is based on a large-scale AI/ML model trained on the real data.

The new paradigm of Fig. 1(d) may be seen to be “evolved” from the direct derivation approach of Fig. 1(c), whereby the “designed-by-the-human” function $s()$ has been replaced by some “learned-by-the-machine” high-dimensional model. But we may equally well consider the new paradigm of Fig. 1(d) to be “evolved” from the low-dimensional parameter fitting approach of Fig. 1(b), whereby the “designed-by-the-human” functions $r()$ and $g()$ have been subsumed into the “learned-by-the-machine” model along with the intermediate set of parameters, and where the low-dimensional set of explicit parameter has been replaced by a high-dimensional one².

Regardless of whether we consider the new paradigm as an “evolution” of one or the other of the two “traditional” approaches, in the passage both *parsimony* and *interpretability* of the process have been lost to some degree, reducing our ability to assess explicitly whether and how much personal information has been conveyed from x into \tilde{x} .

This other risk may have also legal implications (see e.g. the discussion in [9]) but is left out of the scope of our reflection.

² In the case of Variational Auto-Encoder (VAE) architecture, $r()$, z and $g()$ would be naturally mapped respectively to the encoder, subspace and decoder modules thereof.

(a) Genuinely synthetic data

(b) Synthetic data based on low-dimensional data fitting

(c) Semi-synthetic data based on human-designed logic

(d) Pseudo-synthetic data derived from real data via high-dimensional model training

Fig. 1. Taxonomy of “synthetic” data generation paradigms

In the light of the above, we argue that using the term “synthetic” to qualify $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ in the “high-dimensional, non-interpretable” paradigm is misleading, as this term suggests that no relationship is in place between the new data $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ and the real data \mathbf{x} . But a relationship between the two data sets does exist, and without an explicit proof we cannot exclude that such relationship is conducive of personal information. For this reason, we propose to adopt the term “pseudo-synthetic” to refer to the data produced (or reproduced) in this way. Furthermore, this term plays very well with the parallel notion of “pseudonymisation” as defined in GDPR, as discussed hereafter.

3 Privacy-deceptive coding

Let us consider a generic process (procedure, algorithm) taking in input a set of records \mathbf{x} and producing in output a new set of records $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ defined in the same domain. Denote by L the inner working logic of the process. With reference to the system $\mathbf{x} \xrightarrow{L} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ we ask the following question:

In order to certify that the new data set $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ constitutes “anonymous information”, is it possible to rely on a *privacy test* $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{x}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}})$ that considers exclusively the initial and final data sets \mathbf{x} and $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$, *disregarding knowledge about the process L* ?

In other words, we are asking whether it is possible to qualify the new data $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ as “anonymised” by considering the “anonymisation” process L as a black-box, i.e., without knowing all the details and functional logic thereof. We believe that the answer to the above question should be negative, and that detailed knowledge of the process L should be regarded as absolutely necessary to assess whether or not personal information is conveyed into the new data set.

In fact, we conjecture that any “privacy test” $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{x}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}})$ that does not take into account the transformation process can be fooled, i.e., it is possible to design a “dishonest” process L^* that transforms the source data \mathbf{x} into a different form $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ such that the new data (i) pass the test $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{x}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}})$, but at the same time (ii) allows to recover partially or even fully the source data \mathbf{x} . In other words, the “dishonest” process $\mathbf{x} \xrightarrow{L^*} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ is designed to *conceal, rather than remove* personal information from the new data.

We introduce the term “privacy-deceptive coding” to refer to the “dishonest” process L^* . In the next section we provide a possible example of privacy-deceptive coding mechanism. Based on that, we discuss the possibility that even a “honest” large-scale AI/ML generative network that was *not* intentionally designed to do so might end up learning some kind of privacy-deceptive coding scheme. We claim that such a possibility cannot be completely excluded *a priori*, based merely on the analysis of the general architecture of the generative network, but must be checked *a posteriori*, based on the careful audit and interpretation of the structural mechanism that has been actually learned during the training process – a task that may be unfeasible for large models based on the current state-of-the-art in AI/ML explainability and interpretability.

4 An example based on polynomial interpolation

In this section we hint at one example of privacy-deceptive coding scheme. We hope in this way to inspire further research on other similar schemes, and most importantly to investigate the extent by which similar mechanisms may be learned by large-scale generative AI/ML models that were not deliberately designed to do so.

Let us consider a dataset \mathbf{x} consisting of an arbitrary number of records. Each record consists of k “predictor” variables $x_j, j = 1, \dots, k$, plus one “response” variable (or “attribute”). For the sake of simplicity, we assume all predictor variables are continuous and defined over a closed interval $x_j \in [a_j, b_j]$ where the infimum and supremum values a_j, b_j for the j th generic variable are known. The response variable is assumed to be discrete, taking values from an alphabet of m elements. For example, if the data sets represent patient records, the response variable may represent the degree of diagnosis severity on a scale of m levels.

4.1 Interpolation by groups identified by the response value

We group the records by the value of the response variable into m distinct groups. Each group of real records will be mapped to a corresponding group of new pseudo-synthetic records of arbitrary size equal to or larger than the size of the original group. The new group of data will be associated to the same value of the response variable, but will yield different predictor vectors.

Hereafter we show how to encode one generic group, with the understanding that the same procedure can be replicated separately for each of the m groups.

Let n denote the number of data points in the generic group under consideration. The symbol $x_{i,j}$ with $i = 1, \dots, n$ and $j = 1, \dots, k$ will denote the value of the j th variable (column) for the i th element (row). Each record represents a data point in the k -dimensional hypercube.

To encode the n points in the k -dimensional space, we rely on a family of multivariate parametric functions, in a single parameter t and with exactly n degrees of freedom. One obvious choice is to resort to multivariate polynomials of degree $p = n - 1$. A slightly more sophisticated choice would be to resort to multivariate polynomials of degree $p = n + 1$ that are constrained to cross two fixed points of known coordinates placed at opposite corners of the k -dimensional hypercube (“dummy bounding points”). Other variants of the same scheme could adopt different families of parametric functions.

The encoding process goes by first identifying the multivariate function \mathbf{f} , unique in the considered parametric family of curves with n degrees of freedom, that interpolates the ordered set of n points in the group. The function $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{f}(t)$ of the single parameter t defines a 1-dimensional curve (or curved line) in the k -dimensional space. Once that \mathbf{f} has been identified, an alternative set of $\tilde{n} \geq n$ points is chosen along that curve. Each new point corresponds to a different value of the parameter t . The new set of points will unequivocally identify the interpolating function \mathbf{f} . In this way, from the new set of \tilde{n} points it is possible to reconstruct back the curve \mathbf{f} in the k -dimensional space that links together all

the original n points. The new points on the interpolating curve can be selected based on any arbitrary set of criteria, and such criteria can be explicitly crafted to fool the privacy test $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{x}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}})$, e.g., by excluding points that lie “too close” to the original data points.

With this simple generative mechanism, we can produce a new set of data points that passes the privacy test (thanks to the point selection criteria) but still lie on the same interpolating function \mathbf{f} as the original data of the same group. Notably, the new group of $\tilde{n} \geq n$ points allows to reconstruct exactly the interpolating function \mathbf{f} with n degrees of freedom *if the attacker has knowledge of what parametric family of curves was chosen to interpolate the original data points*. This information represents the “auxiliary knowledge”, denoted by \mathcal{I} , that is needed by potential attackers on top of the newly generated data.

Knowledge of \mathcal{I} exposes the new data set $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ to two kinds of privacy attacks, namely attribute discovery and membership inference.

Attribute discovery: Given a predictor vector that is known to be present in the training data set, i.e., a test point in the k -dimensional space, the value of the response variable (attribute) can be discovered by simply checking which one of the m interpolating functions crosses the test point, out of the m functions associated to the different groups. Remember There is a tiny possibility that two interpolating curves for different groups will intersect, and an even smaller probability that the intersection point will fall exactly on the test point. This would lead to a case of ambiguity that, however, would occur with extremely small probability and therefore can be neglected.

Membership inference: Given a predictor vector, it is possible to infer probabilistically whether it corresponds to an element that was present in the training set or not, by merely testing whether its prediction vector falls on any of the m interpolating curves. In the case at hand, the attack yields zero rate of false negatives, since by construction all records in the training dataset lie on some interpolating function. The rate of false positives is non-zero (not all points covered by the interpolating function were present in the original data set) but it vanishes exponentially as the number of variables increases (for a fixed number of training data points n) due to increasing sparsity of a 1-dimensional curve in the k -dimensional space for increasing k .

These two attacks, namely attribute discovery and membership inference, represent *partial* recovery of original data from the “new” data. With a little additional sophistication of the encoding process it is possible to enable the *full* recovery of the original group of data points, thus enabling a full database reconstruction attack, or equivalently the full “decoding” of the original data. Towards this aim, one possibility would be to select the new data points in correspondence of parameter values \tilde{t}_i ’s that can be deterministically referred back to the original values t_i , e.g., choosing $\tilde{t}_i = t_i + \Delta$ (whereby Δ is a fixed salt) or as mid-points between consecutive real points $\tilde{t}_i = (t_{i+1} - t_i) / 2$. There

are numerous other strategies to achieve the same goal. For the attack to be successful, the attacker must gain additional knowledge about the criterion that was adopted to select the \tilde{t}_i 's, and such knowledge adds up to the previous one about the parametric family of choice. In other words, the “auxiliary information” \mathcal{I} that is necessary to fully decode the data grows together with the sophistication of the encoding process.

These simple hints should suffice to show that it is indeed possible to “encode” entirely the original data in a new data set that is only apparently different at face value from the real data but carries the whole information thereof. If the new data set is disseminated publicly, then the protection of the original training data rests entirely on the secrecy of the auxiliary knowledge \mathcal{K} . This has certain legal consequences that will be elaborated later in Section ??.

4.2 Interpretation: interpolating line as latent space

It is useful at this stage to establish a bridge between the interpolating example presented above and the terminology in use in AI/ML model architectures. The multivariate single-parameter interpolating curve $\mathbf{f}(t)$ may be interpreted as one (among the many possible) “latent subspace” embedding the group of training points. In principle, the so-called “hidden layer” of a Variational Auto-Encoder (VAE) network may just end up “discovering” this interpolating curve, or some other curve that is functionally equivalent to it.

The training points are not the only ones laying on this curve (equivalently: in this subspace), but compared to the entire volume of k -dimensional hypercube the 1-dimensional curve represents a subspace that is “wrapped tightly” around the original points. This is, in essence, why the identification of the interpolating curve \mathbf{f} opens the door to attribute discovery and membership inference attacks with very high accuracy (zero false negatives, low false positives). Based on this consideration, we believe that the interpolating curve \mathbf{f} itself may be plausibly considered as “personal data” in terms of GDPR.

It is legitimate to ask whether the “latent subspace” learned by large-scale network (e.g., in the VAE architecture) to which the training points are mapped, and from which all the new points are extracted, displays similar properties as the interpolating curve \mathbf{f} defined above. Does it “wrap tightly” the training points? Can it be re-identified by the new data points?

To the extent that the answer to these questions is “possibly yes”, then disclosing the new data represents a considerable hazard. In our opinion, to the extent that the interpolating curve is represented into the trained model – or equivalently that the “latent subspace” learned by the network amounts to some kind of interpolating curve that “wraps tightly” the training points – then the model should qualify as “personal data” in GDPR terms – a point that has been claimed already elsewhere [10].

(a) Dishonest setting designed to maximise “utility” for the attacker (b) Honest setting designed to maximise “utility” for the analyst

Fig. 2. Examples of architectures for data generation aimed at maximising “utility” while passing the “privacy test”. The training signals are derived from the scores in the privacy and utility tests. The utility test is defined different for the dishonest and honest setting, but the latter can be considered as a relaxation of the former.

5 Automatic learning of privacy-deceptive coding

In the previous section we have hinted at some examples of human-designed privacy-deceptive coding schemes. With a little additional effort one could devise other similar mechanisms and variants thereof. In this section we elaborate on the possibility for a large-scale AI/ML model to learn some sort of similar privacy-deceptive coding scheme, i.e., a mechanism to encode the source data set \mathbf{x} into the new data set $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ in a way that is reversible and allows an “attacker” to recover back the source data, in parts (attributes, memberships) or in full, from the new “generated” pseudo-synthetic data plus some auxiliary knowledge \mathcal{I} .

We do not make any assumption on the particular architecture of the generative AI/ML model, other than assuming that it is over-parameterised. A recent survey shows that Variational Auto-Encoders (VAE) are Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) are among the most popular architectures in this field [11], but our discussion at this early stage is abstract and addresses any large-scale network, independently from the particular architecture.

Before progressing further, a note on terminology is due. We will use the term “encoder” to refer to any system that, taking in input the source data \mathbf{x} , produces in output a new data set $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ that embeds partial or full information from the source data. Conversely, we use the term “decoder” to refer to a system that recovers the source data \mathbf{x} from the encoded data $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$. In the scope of this section, the “encoder” is represented by a large-scale AI/ML model trained on real data³. Our use of the terms “encoder” and “decoder” is rather inspired by

³ Our use of these terms should not be confused with the meaning that they have in the context of autoencoder architectures, where the same terms are used to refer to spe-

Information Theory, and specifically by the theory of Channel Coding. In fact, we regard the problem of exfiltrating personal information as a particular type of channel coding problem where the source message \mathbf{x} is to be transferred across a “channel” that allows only transmission of data complying with the given “privacy test” $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{x}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}})$. Therefore, the source message \mathbf{x} must be “encoded” in the new form $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ to pass through the channel.

Armed with this terminology, we show in Fig. 2(a) how the high-level schema of a possible “dishonest” system, designed intentionally to learn some privacy-deceptive coding scheme. In Fig. 2(a) the “encoder” and “decoder” modules refer to distinct but coupled networks that are trained jointly on the same signals, and may possibly share some layers. Their joint goal is to produce a reversible encoding mechanism that produces “encoded” pseudo-synthetic data $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{x}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}})$ that pass the privacy test while at the same time allowing the corresponding decoding mechanisms to reconstruct, in full or in part, the source data \mathbf{x} . The signals that drive the learning process, i.e., the loss function, is based on the scores of the two test modules shown in the figure: the first module tests for “privacy”, in the sense of compliance to the “privacy test” $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{x}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}})$. The second module at the bottom tests for “utility” *for the attacker* by comparing the reconstructed data to the original data.

It is clear that only a “dishonest” analyst could be motivated to implement deliberately the architecture of Fig. 2(a). The only conceivable practical use of such system, beyond legitimate experimental research, would be to setup a personal data exfiltration scam. The “encoder” module trained in this way would be presented as a genuine “synthetic data generator”. If the only condition to certify the “non personal” nature of the data $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{x}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}})$ relied on the privacy test $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$, based exclusively on the “appearance” of the data $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ and oblivious to the mechanism by which they were produced, then sharing the (pseudo)-synthetic data $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ would be considered legally acceptable notwithstanding that it effectively amount to a mere exfiltration of the real data \mathbf{x} .

We now move from the “dishonest” to the “honest” scenario. In this case the analyst does not pursue explicitly the reconstruction of the original data from the (pseudo-)synthetic data, but rather aims to preserve their “utility” for certain legitimate analysis tasks, i.e., to allow some large-scale AI/ML inference model to return correct results based on the pseudo-synthetic data. Towards this aim, the honest analyst may adopt the architecture of Fig. 2(b). In the new scheme, the “utility” of the pseudo-synthetic data is expressed in terms of their ability to drive a large-scale AI/ML model trained on such data to deliver correct inference results, ideally the very same results that would have been obtained by training the same model on the real data.

The “utility” goal expressed in this way, from the perspective of the honest analyst, may be considered as a relaxation of the “full data reconstruction” goal adopted by the dishonest analyst: indeed, the ability to reconstruct the source

cific layers of the network. If a VAE network is used to produce the (pseudo-)synthetic data, the whole VAE network, comprehensive of its inner “encoder”, “decoder” and “hidden” layers, would represent the “encoder” system in our schema.

data is a sufficient condition to guarantee full utility of the pseudo-synthetic data. In principle, we cannot completely exclude *a priori* that the “honest” architecture ends-up learning (and embedding into the “encoder” module) some kind of reversible mapping mechanism, similar to the privacy-deceptive scheme learned by the “dishonest” architecture, with the inference model downstream learning the corresponding “decoding” scheme.

We do not intend to postulate here that learning such a privacy-deceptive scheme is necessarily the only possible outcome of honest learning. However, we conjecture that this is a possible *and plausible* outcome that cannot be excluded *a priori*. Some very recent empirical work provide early clues that our claim may be more than just a conjecture. In an experimental setting similar to the “honest analyst” scenario described above, the authors of [12] report that “*The ML model trained on the synthetic data [...] was found to leak in the same way or slightly less than the original classifier*” (quoted from [12, p. 15]). Other authors in [13] find that the value of a sensitive attribute associated to a real record in the original data set can be inferred back from a set of (pseudo-)synthetic data that do not appear to contain that specific record (but obviously “encode” such information in some hidden form). Our work is complementary to these parallel empirical work in that the privacy-deceptive coding scheme introduced above provide early hints about the the kind of underlying structural mechanism that may possibly explain those empirical findings.

While these empirical studies do not provide a conclusive proof, they represent initial clues in support of the hypothesis that (pseudo-)synthetic data generated by deep learning models may represent the outcome of some privacy-deceptive coding scheme that was “learned” by the generative model at the training stage. Recognising this possibility as plausible should be sufficient, by the principle of precaution, to put the “burden of the proof” on the proponents of this approach, i.e., on the “honest” analysts willing to leverage deep learning for the production of (pseudo-)synthetic data. Before qualifying the new data as “anonymous” they should be required to demonstrate *a posteriori* that the mechanism that was actually learned by their AI/ML model does not embed any kind of implicit privacy-deceptive coding. Doing so requires a thorough explanation and interpretation of what the network has actually learned, a task that may be simply unfeasible for large-scale networks with billions of parameters given the current state-of-the-art in AI/ML explainability. Without such formal guarantees, the data $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ produced (or reproduced) by deep learning on the personal data \mathbf{x} should not be considered as “anonymised” data, but rather as personal data in protected form.

If the large-scale generative process was to perform some kind of privacy-deceptive coding, the data generator process may be considered similar to an encryption system, for which the decryption key \mathcal{K} must be kept separate from the encrypted data (cipher-text) $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$. The data holder willing to pass the pseudo-synthetic data $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ to other entities, or even release it publicly, remains legally obliged to ensure that none of the receiving entities will ever be able to obtain, infer or simply guess the auxiliary knowledge \mathcal{K} that enables partial or full

recovery of the original data \mathbf{x} . This in turn implies an effort to analyse and understand in depth the generation process in order to identify what auxiliary information would be needed, where it lies, whether and how a potential attacker could obtain it, and ultimately how to protect it. These requirements create additional work and responsibilities for the data holders, and reduce the appeal of pseudo-synthetic data as a quick win solution in real-world applications.

6 Conclusive remarks

There is already wide empirical evidence⁴ that deep learning models, like a sponge immersed in a liquid, tend to “absorb” personal information from the personal data on which they are trained, and that such information can be then “squeezed out” from the trained model by means of so-called “model inversion attacks”. Similarly, we expect in the near future a proliferation of papers on “synthetic data inversion attacks”, i.e., empirical studies showing that also the (pseudo-)synthetic data generated by deep learning models may carry personal information from the original training data, and that such information can be inferred back partially (as in attribute discovery and membership inference attacks) or even fully (as in database reconstruction attacks). In this perspective, recent works like [12,13] are just the first pioneering examples of a line of research that, we expect, will be growing in the few coming years.

In parallel to empirical studies devoted to demonstrate empirically the feasibility of privacy attacks against (pseudo-)synthetic data, it is important to unveil the general structural mechanisms underlying the phenomenon, i.e., to explain *how* and *why* personal information flows through the model into the newly generated data. In this preliminary contribution we have attempted to take a first step in this direction by formulating an initial hypothesis inspired by the concept of parametric interpolation.

We hope that the conceptual framework, the terminology and the bridge with Channel Coding Theory proposed in this initial paper will contribute to accelerate further research on the limitations of (pseudo-)synthetic data generated based on deep learning. At the same time, we hope that it will contribute, together with other prominent work in the field [3,4], to raise awareness among legal experts, data protection officers and potential adopters that (pseudo-)synthetic data based on deep learning are not a risk-free approach to the data protection problem, but rather an approach for which risks are yet to be fully understood.

Disclaimer The view expressed in this paper are those of the author and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission.

Acknowledgments. Thanks to Angelo Coluccia and Giuseppe D’Acquisto for a series of insightful discussions that fueled and challenged the initial ideas at the inception of this work.

⁴ The interested reader may refer to the ample bibliography available from <https://github.com/AndrewZhou924/Awesome-model-inversion-attack>

Disclosure of Interests. The author has no competing interests.

References

1. A. Hundepool, J. Domingo-Ferrer, L. Franconi, S. Giessing, E. Nordholt, K. Spicer, and P. de Wolf, *Statistical Disclosure Control*. John Wiley & Sons, 2012.
2. A. Calvino, “A simple method for limiting disclosure in continuous microdata based on principal component analysis,” *Journal of Official Statistics*, vol. 33, no. 1, p. 15–41, 2017. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1515/JOS-2017-0002>.
3. T. Stadler and C. Troncoso, “Why the search for a privacy-preserving data sharing mechanism is failing,” *Nature Computational Science*, vol. 2, p. 208–210, 2022. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43588-022-00236-x>.
4. T. Stadler, B. Oprisanu, and C. Troncoso, “Synthetic data—anonimisation groundhog day,” in *USENIX*, 2022. Available at: https://www.usenix.org/system/files/sec22summer_stadler.pdf.
5. S. Theodoridis, *Machine Learning: A Bayesian and Optimization Perspective (2nd Edition)*. Elsevier, 2020.
6. M. Belkin, S. Ma, and S. Mandal, “To understand deep learning we need to understand kernel learning,” in *Proc. of the 35th Int. Conf. on Machine Learning (PMLR 80)*, 2018. Available at: <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v80/belkin18a.html>.
7. M. Belkin, D. Hsueh, S. Ma, and S. Mandal, “Reconciling modern machine-learning practice and the classical bias–variance trade-off,” *PNAS*, vol. 116, no. 32, pp. 15849–15854, 2019. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1903070116>.
8. INEXDA working group, “Main outcomes of the INEXDA working group on statistical disclosure control (sdc),” 2024. Available at: https://www.inexda.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/Final_Report_INEXDA_WG_SDC_20240422.pdf.
9. G. D’Acquisto, “Dati sintetici: cosa sono, le applicazioni e i rischi da gestire,” May 2024. Available at: <https://www.agendadigitale.eu/sicurezza/privacy/dati-sintetici-cosa-sono-le-applicazioni-e-i-rischi-da-gestire> (in Italian).
10. M. Veale, R. Binns, and L. Edwards, “Algorithms that remember: model inversion attacks and data protection law,” *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A*, vol. 376, 2018. Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2018.0083>.
11. Y. Lu, M. Shen, H. Wang, X. Wang, C. van Rechem, and W. Wei, “Machine learning for synthetic data generation: A review,” January 2024. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/html/2302.04062v6>.
12. M. Slokom, P. de Wolf, and M. Larson, “When machine learning models leak: An exploration of synthetic training data,” in *Privacy in Statistical Databases (PSD)*, 2022. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.08775>.
13. M. Annamalai, A. Gadotti, and L. Rocher, “A linear reconstruction approach for attribute inference attacks against synthetic data,” in *33th Usenix Security Symposium*, 2024. Extended version available at: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2301.10053>.